

DAMAGE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES FOR VARIOUS MECHANICAL LOADS

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Keywords: Composite plates, Matrix damage, Fibre rupture

ABSTRACT

A generalized non-linear cumulative Continuum Damage Mechanics (*CDM*) model for unidirectional and woven plies laminates undergoing static and fatigue loads has been developed. The damage, consisting of small cracks running parallel to the fibers, leads to a loss of stiffness in the transverse and shear directions. Even if the sizes of these cracks correspond to the thickness of the ply, they do not lead in general to the rupture of the laminate. On the other hand, the rupture of one ply in the fibre direction is in general catastrophic for the laminate and the structure. A model defined at the ply scale to describe the rupture in the fibre direction for statics and fatigue loadings was proposed. This model is based on a reduction of strength in the fibre direction for high levels of transverse damage. This phenomenon of reduction of strength in the fibre direction for high levels of transverse damage can also be observed on 0° tubular specimen solicited in fatigue in torsion up to a high level of damage followed by a tensile or compressive test in the fibre direction.

The *CDM* model describes the evolution of the damage depending on the combined shear/transverse load. The effect of the shear load can be studied using a [45,-45]_{ns} laminates in traction. In the case of unbalanced woven plies, the transverse behavior can be studied using a [90°]_{ns} laminates. In the case of a traction on a *UD* plies [90°]_{ns} laminate, the first small crack (less than the thickness of the ply) in the transverse direction leads to the rupture of the laminate. It is proposed here to study the transverse and shear effects on the evolution of the damage using [60,-60]_{ns} and [50,-50]_{ns} *UD* ply laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

The damage, consisting of small cracks running parallel to the fibers, leads to a loss of stiffness in the transverse and shear directions [1,2]. A model based on a Continuum Damage Mechanics (*CDM*) approach was developed to simulate *UD*, balanced and unbalanced woven ply laminates under static and fatigue loading conditions [2,3]. Even if the sizes of these cracks correspond to the thickness of the ply, they do not lead in general to the rupture of the laminate. On the other hand, the rupture of one ply in the fibre direction is in general catastrophic for the laminate and the structure. A model defined on the ply scale to describe the rupture in the fibre direction for statics and fatigue loadings was proposed [4]. This model is based on a reduction of strength in the fibre direction for high levels of transverse damage. For unidirectional carbon fibre plies, loaded in the fibres direction only, strength is not appreciably modified in fatigue [2]. For balanced woven plies with glass or carbon fibres, strength in the fibres direction decreases in fatigue [3,4]. Indeed, the woven plies can be regarded as a [0°, 90°] laminate with “virtual” unidirectional plies which undergo a transverse positive traction stress in the 0° “virtual” unidirectional ply for a tensile test on the woven ply [3]. This phenomenon of reduction of strength in the fibre direction for high levels of transverse damage can also be observed on 0° tubular specimen solicited in fatigue in torsion up to a level of high damage followed by a tensile test in the fibre direction. New tests on tubular specimen damaged after a torsion load and then loaded in compression show that the reduction of strength appears earlier for compression load in the fibre direction.

The *CDM* model describes the evolution of the damage and inelastic strain depending on the combined shear/transverse load and the maximum/amplitude of the load during a cycle as well as the level of damage involved. The effect of the shear load can be studied using a $[45,-45]_{ns}$ laminates in traction. In the case of unbalanced woven plies, the transverse behavior can be studied using a $[90^\circ]_{ns}$ laminates. This model was validated on out of-axis tests, on other stacking sequences laminates in traction and on tubes under torsion/traction [3]. In the case of *UD* plies, the transverse behavior is more difficult to study. In the case of a traction on a *UD* plies $[90^\circ]_{ns}$ laminate, the first small crack (less than the thickness of the ply) in the transverse direction leads to the rupture of the laminate [2]. It is proposed here to study the transverse and shear effects on the evolution of the damage under static and fatigue loads using $[60,-60]_{ns}$ and $[50,-50]_{ns}$ *UD* ply laminates.

2 MODELING OF THE PLY DAMAGEABLE BEHAVIOR

A model based on the Continuum Damage Mechanics (*CDM*) has been developed to describe the damageable behaviour of composite material at the ply scale [2,3]. The damage is assumed to be uniform in the thickness of the ply. The modelling of both static and fatigue loadings with the same model is allowed by the use of a non-linear cumulative law which describes the damage evolution according to the maximal load and the amplitude of the cyclic loading.

In the fibre direction, the *UD* ply shows linear elastic behaviour in response to tension loading until the final brittle failure. In the transverse and shear directions, the behaviour is non-linear due to the damages which lead to a decrease in stiffness. The damage kinematics was described by three internal damage variables:

- d_1 , whose evolution represents the linear elastic behaviour and the brittle failure of the fibres observed in response to tension loading applied in the longitudinal direction
- d_2 , which models the lost of transverse stiffness resulting from transverse and shear loadings
- d_{12} , which describes the decrease in shear stiffness due to transverse and shear loadings.

The gradual development of both damage d_2 and d_{12} depends on the tension load as well as on the shear load, which generates the matrix cracks. Assuming the existence of plane stresses and small perturbations, the strain energy in the ply can be written as follows [1]:

$$E_D^{ps} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_1 \rangle_+^2}{E_1^0 (1-d_1)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_1 \rangle_-^2}{E_1^0} + \frac{\langle \sigma_2 \rangle_+^2}{E_2^0 (1-d_2)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_2 \rangle_-^2}{E_2^0} - 2 \frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0 (1-d_{12})} \right] \quad (1)$$

where $\langle . \rangle_+$ is the positive part and $\langle . \rangle_-$ is the negative part. The tension energy and the compression energy are split in order to describe the unilateral nature of the damage process due to the opening and closing of the cracks. The thermodynamic forces associated with the internal tension and shear variables d_1 , d_2 and d_{12} are defined as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} Y_{d_i} = \frac{\partial E_D^{ps}}{\partial d_i} = \frac{\langle \sigma_i \rangle_+^2}{2E_i^0 (1-d_i)^2} \quad \text{with } i = 1, 2 \\ Y_{d_{12}} = \frac{\partial E_D^{ps}}{\partial d_{12}} = \frac{(\sigma_{12})^2}{2G_{12}^0 (1-d_{12})^2} \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

The development of internal variables depends on these thermodynamic forces. Under tension loading conditions, d_1 has to develop suddenly to model the brittle behaviour in the fibre direction. So, d_1 is defined as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} d_1 = 0 \quad \text{if } Y_{d_1} < Y_1^{\max} \\ d_1 = 1 \quad \text{if } Y_{d_1} \geq Y_1^{\max} \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where Y_1^{\max} is the parameter defining the ultimate force in the fibre direction

The cumulative damage evolution law is defined as follow where the damage variables in the transverse and the shear directions, denoted respectively d_2 and d_{12} , are obtained by adding the terms due to static and fatigue loadings.

$$d_2 = d_2^s + d_2^f \quad (4)$$

$$d_{12} = c d_2 \quad (5)$$

In the case of static loading, the tension/shear coupling during the development of d_2^s and d_{12}^s is accounted for by the following equivalent thermodynamic force:

$$Y_{eq} = a \left(Y_{d_2^s} \right)^n + b \left(Y_{d_{12}^s} \right)^m \quad (6)$$

where a, b, m and n are material parameters specifying the tension/shear coupling. The evolution law for the damage is written as:

$$d_2^s = \left\langle 1 - e^{-\left(Y_{eq} - Y_0^s \right)} \right\rangle_+ \quad (7)$$

where the constant parameter Y_0^s corresponds to the threshold value of the development of d_2^s (which ranges from 0 to 1) and d_{12}^s is proportional to d_2^s .

In the case of fatigue loading, damage evolution depends on the maximal load $Y_{d_i^f}$ and the amplitude of the loading $\Delta Y_{d_i^f}$ during a cycle. The damage evolution law is then written as:

$$\frac{\partial d_2^f}{\partial N} = (1 - d_2)^\gamma \left\langle a_f \left(Y_{d_2^f} \right)^{\beta_1} \left(\Delta Y_{d_2^f} \right)^{\beta_2} + b_f \left(Y_{d_{12}^f} \right)^{\beta_3} \left(\Delta Y_{d_{12}^f} \right)^{\beta_4} - Y_0^f \right\rangle_+ \quad (8)$$

Where Y_0^f is the threshold value of the development of d_2^f

$$\Delta Y_{d_2^f} = \frac{\left(\langle \sigma_2^{\max} \rangle_+ - \langle \sigma_2^{\min} \rangle_+ \right)^2}{2 E_2^0 (1 - d_2^f)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta Y_{d_{12}^f} = \frac{\left(\sigma_{12}^{\max} - \sigma_{12}^{\min} \right)^2}{2 G_{12}^0 (1 - d_{12}^f)^2} \quad (9)$$

3 SHEAR AND TRANSVERSE DAMAGE

The effect of the shear load can be studied using a [45,-45]_{ns} laminates in traction. For this laminate and in the case of carbon fibre, the ratio of the shear/transverse stress is equal to 6,25. The stress/strain curve shows the evolution of the damage in red (Figure 1) and allowed to identify the shear damage law (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Stress/strain curve of the [45,-45]_{ns}

Figure 2. Evolution of the shear damage

In the case of unbalanced woven plies, the transverse behaviour can be studied using a $[90^\circ]_{ns}$ laminates [3]. In the case of UD plies, the transverse behaviour is more difficult to study [3]. In the case of a traction on a UD plies $[90^\circ]_{ns}$ laminate, the first small crack (less than the thickness of the ply) in the transverse direction leads to the rupture of the laminate and the level of the strain and damage is very low (0,3%).

It is proposed here to study the transverse and shear effects on the evolution of the damage under static and fatigue loads using $[\theta, -\theta]_{ns}$ laminates. It was proposed in [1] to use a $[67, -67]_{ns}$ laminate to study the transverse behaviour but this laminate still showed a brittle behaviour. In the case of $[60, -60]_{ns}$ laminate corresponding to a shear/transverse stress ratio equal to 0,66, it can be observed a softening behaviour (Figure 3) and an instability fracture corresponding to a high level of damage (Figure 4). This test allowed to identify the transverse parameter of the damage law.

Figure 3. Stress/strain curve of the $[60, -60]_{ns}$

Figure 4. Evolution of the damage

In order to validate the law under a combined load, it is possible to do a test on a $[50, -50]_{ns}$ laminate corresponding to a shear/transverse stress ratio equal to 1,8. It can be observed again a softening behaviour (Figure 5) and an instability fracture corresponding to a high level of damage (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Stress/strain curve of the $[50, -50]_{ns}$

Figure 6. Evolution of the damage

4 FIBER TENSILE FAILURE CRITERION

During the loading, crack density increases in the transverse direction and this damage leads to a decrease of the stiffness. In the longitudinal direction, the damage disrupts the load transfer between fibers. Fiber failure can then occur even if the maximal stress usually measured in the case of homogeneous tension test is not reached. This phenomenon was not observed in the case of static loading due to the weak crack density compared to the case of fatigue loading where the damage can reach a very high level.

Experimental tests were performed to study this phenomenon which can lead to premature failure of laminate. Specific tubes were manufactured with Glass/Epoxy unbalanced woven ply. The tube shape was studied so that the strains field was homogeneous in the central area (Figure 7). The lay-up in the central area was (0)₃. Torsion cyclic loading was applied to the tubes to generate matrix damage. The rotation was limited to avoid applying load on fibers. Stress/Strain curves were plotted to evaluate the decrease of stiffness which characterize the evolution of the damage as we can see on Figure 8. Various levels of damage were obtained according to the number of cycles applied. Then, the tubes were loaded in static tension until the final failure to estimate the residual strength of the fibers. Figure 9 shows the influence of the damage on the strength at failure in the fiber direction. Because of specimen complexity and test duration, the results are limited but it appears clearly that a high level of damage leads to a decrease of the strength in the fiber direction.

Figure 7. Geometry of the tube

Figure 8. Stiffness decrease during the cycles

Figure 9. Strength at failure with respect to damage

The Figure 10 confirms that the decrease of strength is mainly due to matrix damage. The Load/Displacement curves were plotted for safe and damaged tubes. Fiber damage would affect the stiffness of the specimen.

Tests showed the strong influence of the matrix damage on the fiber failure. Because of matrix cracking and matrix/fibre debonding, the load transfer between fibers could not be fully. Failure of the ply occurred although the stress in the fiber direction was lower than the tensile failure strength.

For a fiber failure model, the matrix damage is evaluated and its influence on the fibers strength can be taken into account with the following simple criterion:

$$Y_{d_1} \leq Y_{d_1}^{\max}(d_2) \quad (10)$$

where the thermodynamic force Y_{d_1} is proportional to the longitudinal stress (Refer to eq.(3)) and d_2 is the transverse damage in the UD ply. $Y_{d_1}^{\max}$ evolves sharply between two values according to a threshold value of d_2 as it was shown in Figure 11. In the case of static loading, the level of damage does not usually reach the threshold and the criterion (10) is equivalent to a maximal stress criterion. But in the case of fatigue loading with a high number of cycles, the level of the damage cannot be neglected.

Figure 10. Tension tests on damaged tubes Figure 11. $Y_{d_1}^{\max}$ evolution law with respect to damage

New tests on tubular specimen damaged after a torsion load (Figure 12) and then loaded in compression show that the reduction of strength appears earlier for compression load in the fibre direction (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Tension tests on damaged tubes Figure 13. $Y_{d_1}^{\max}$ evolution law with respect to damage

5 CONCLUSIONS

A model based on the reduction of strength in the fibre direction, under tension and compression load, reduction depending on the level of transverse damage, was developed. The evolution of the transverse damage is described by a CDM model, under static and fatigue loadings. It was proposed here to study the evolution of the damage under transverse stress on $[60,-60]_{ns}$ laminates in the case of unidirectional plies. Other tests to study the evolution of damage for high constant load and for different load speed are under investigation.

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